

IRIS GUIDELINES

for authors affiliated with the University of Trento

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1. About IRIS

[IRIS – Institutional Research Information System](#) is an open-access institutional repository that contains the scientific output published by authors affiliated with the University of Trento.

The IRIS system may consist of several modules: Research Catalogue (Institutional Repository - IR), Resource Management, Activities and Projects, and Scientific Evaluation (Evaluation and Review - ER). IRIS UniTrento includes only the IR and ER modules.

IRIS IR replaces the UGOV platform (2010-2015).

IRIS was updated on 11 July 2022 to the [DSpace 6](#) version, improving compatibility with all navigation software, particularly mobile devices.

2. What is IRIS for

[IRIS](#) is the single entry point for strategic information across all internal and external research processes, including evaluation and monitoring. It also enables the dissemination of bibliographic data and full-text publications when the author has legally deposited them in Open Access. More in detail:

- **Ministerial evaluation:** IRIS provides bibliographic data to the [LoginMIUR](#) ministerial database, enabling the [Ministry of University and Research](#) ([ASN](#), [VQR](#), [SUA-RD](#), [Doctoral Accreditation](#), [PRIN](#), [FFABR](#)) to conduct evaluation processes. For ASN, IRIS enables monitoring of the candidate's or potential commissioner's position through a dedicated reporting function (see Chapter 13). For VQR (see Chapter 14), IRIS complements the 'Institutional Repository' (IR) input module with the 'Evaluation and Review' (ER) module;
- **Open Access dissemination:** IRIS allows Open Access dissemination of the University's scientific research output (see Chapter 5), through the [OpenAIRE](#) portal as well (with which it is synchronized), as required by EU research calls for applications ([FP7](#), [H2020](#), [Horizon Europe](#));
- **Research monitoring:** IRIS enables the production of reports for the University Evaluation Board, the Quality Committee, the Departments, and the Centers to monitor the productivity of the University's academic structures, as well as for evaluation purposes (salary increases, internal career advancements, and the distribution of departmental and [excellence](#) funds).

- **[Legal deposit of doctoral theses](#)**: IRIS promotes the dissemination of young researchers' work by archiving their doctoral theses, which are mandatorily and automatically deposited via IRIS in the [National Central Libraries of Rome](#) and [Florence](#).
- **Valorization of the University's scientific output**: IRIS records with status 'In validation' or 'Validated' are displayed on the web page of recognized University of Trento authors in the 'Publication' sector of their page on the [Trento Digital University](#) portal. Draft or reopened records are not displayed in this section.

3. Who Has Access to IRIS

Authors affiliated with the [University of Trento](#), contributing to the scientific output of the [University Departments and Research Structures](#), are **required** to enter their publications in the IRIS [UniTrento Research Register \(Anagrafe della Ricerca\)](#).

The following categories of authors can access IRIS by logging in with their UniTrento credentials: professors, professors on fixed-term contracts, researchers, researchers on fixed-term contracts and tenure-track, other academic staff, grant holders, PhD students, collaborators, and administrative and technical staff.

As a bibliographic search tool, IRIS can be used by all web users (including students) without [logging in](#) to identify publications by UniTrento academic staff and to check their fields of interest. If the PDFs of such publications are not directly downloadable from IRIS (because they are not openly accessible, i.e., Open Access), they can be searched through the [Trentino Bibliographic Catalogue \(CBT\)](#) ('Catalogo Bibliografico Trentino', CBT) or the [Periodicals Catalogue](#) ('Catalogo dei Periodici'), and requested [for loan](#) or [interlibrary loan](#) ('prestito interbibliotecario').

4. How to Log in to IRIS

Authors can access [IRIS](#) using their [institutional account](#) according to the instructions and rules on the [IRIS portal in the 'Guide per autori e autrici' \(Author's Guide sections\)](#).

Authors in the roles indicated in paragraph 3 are automatically enabled to log in using their University of Trento username and password at the following URL: <https://iris.unitn.it/>

IRIS can also be accessed via the *Produzione scientifica* ('Scientific Production') widget on [MyUnitn](#).

5. Databases, archives, and external platforms interoperability with IRIS

Each author's bibliography is **not automatically transferred to IRIS** but must be entered progressively by the author, either manually or in one of the 'automatized' ways (see Chapter 7) that make the transfer of bibliographic metadata easier.

IRIS IR serves as the sole **official single-entry point** for strategic information across all internal and external **research processes at UniTrento**, and it is interoperable with the main national and international databases. Thanks to standard formats and *ad hoc* communication protocols, it reliably and resource-optimally exchanges information and services with other databases. It is therefore possible to export metadata (bibliographic records) and data (full-text PDFs) from IRIS to different databases (outbound interoperability) and/or to import them (inbound interoperability), operating on individual records or entire sets of records. This eliminates the need to retype the same information across multiple databases manually.

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Every database has its own specific function, which determines the type and amount of information it contains (and exports).

IRIS (only partially shared with LoginMIUR) can be compared to citation and bibliometric databases (e.g., SCOPUS, Web of Science), disciplinary repositories (e.g., PubMed, ArXiv), generalist Open Access repositories (e.g., Zenodo), and sites such as ORCID, OpenAIRE, or journal publishing platforms that display scientific products in Open Access.

IRIS's specific function is to evaluate research output in accordance with ministerial and ANVUR (National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research) criteria.

Therefore, IRIS provides specific fields that **match the particular information needs of MUR and ANVUR, and these data cannot be automatically imported into IRIS from other databases or sites** such as WoS, SCOPUS, ArXiv, and PubMed. These external sources are therefore only partially usable for the direct transfer to LoginMIUR of the information they contain.

These **specific fields have to be completed manually in IRIS by the author** of the scientific product. **The automatic import from databases or archives is therefore NOT the final action** in IRIS. However, it

must be followed by entering all the data still missing after the import, whether they are compulsory (marked with an asterisk) or optional but strategic for evaluation purposes (e.g., ISBN, SCOPUS ID, WoS ID, etc.), as established by the relevant Guidelines and Manuals (see Chapter 17).

The main databases or sites exchanging data and services with IRIS (inbound or outbound) are:

DATABASE	INBOUND INTEROPERABILITY (to IRIS)	OUTBOUND INTEROPERABILITY (from IRIS)	SYNCHRONIZATION TIME
Open policy finder (publishing policies) <i>formerly Sherpa Romeo</i>	X		Real-time
DOAJ (publishing policies)	X		Real-time
Unpaywall (publishing policies)	X		Real-time
Web of Science (bibliometrics, bibliographies in files of any format, and/or bibliographic descriptions of an individual product)	X		Data on journal percentiles and JCR/WoS journal indices (Impact Factor, Eigenfactor, article influence, etc.) are related to the latest available year. The uploaded data refers to the publisher's latest update.

<p>SCOPUS (bibliometrics, bibliographies in any file format, and/or bibliographic descriptions of a single product)</p>	<p>X</p>		<p>Journal SCOPUS index data (SJR, SNIP, Citescore) are related to the latest available year. The uploaded data refers to the publisher's latest update.</p>
<p>arXiv (OA archive)</p>	<p>X</p>		<p>Real-time query (the incoming data are those displayed on the publishers' web services).</p>
<p>PubMed (biomedical science literature)</p>	<p>X</p>		<p>Real-time query (the incoming data are those displayed on the publishers' web services).</p>
<p>OpenAlex (bibliographic catalogue of scientific articles, authors, and institutions accessible in open access mode)</p>	<p>X</p>		<p>Real-time query (the incoming data are those displayed on the publishers' web services).</p>

<p>ORCID (site of researchers' profiles linked to a unique persistent identifier)</p>	<p>X</p>	<p>X</p>	<p>Pull - Importing products from ORCID = real-time.</p> <p>Push - Data transfer to ORCID (only publications modified/entered the day before and in final status) = 24 hours.</p>
<p>mEDRA (European DOI Registration Agency)</p>	<p>X</p>		<p>Real-time query (the incoming data are those displayed on the publishers' web services).</p>
<p>CiNii (bibliographic database for material from Japanese academic libraries)</p>	<p>X</p>		<p>Real-time query (the incoming data are those displayed on the publishers' web services).</p>
<p>People / Trento Digital University (address book and University Dashboard with information and statistics on people and structures)</p>		<p>X</p>	<p>24-28 hours after insertion in IRIS.</p>

LoginMIUR (CINECA Academic staff webpage)	Import to be requested to IRIS administrators.	X	<p>Every night: new or amended publications. Weekly: publications with a notice of non-submission (warning).</p> <p>Authors as well as administrators can force synchronization via a special button in the record. Synchronization will be made in real time, but synchronization times may slow down in periods of evaluation deadlines.</p>
OpenAIRE (EU-funded research output dataset)		X	<p>Every week after insertion/modification in IRIS.</p>

Finally, IRIS IR also exchanges data via Business Intelligence Reporting and Analysis (ODS) for extractions, statistics, and ASN simulation. Synchronization occurs approximately every 3-4 hours during daylight hours, Monday to Friday, and once a day on Saturdays.

6. I am a new member of the University academic staff: what should I do?

If you come from a university with an IRIS institutional research repository, in which you have already entered your publications, or if you have already entered your publications in the 'LoginMIUR' academic staff site, please contact the Research Outputs Office (iris@unitn.it) for information on the best procedure.

The suggested procedure is to grant permission to the Research Outputs Office to perform a bulk import from LoginMIUR of all previously submitted primary evaluation data required by MUR and ANVUR, as well as all PDF attachments previously entered by the author. Importing from SCOPUS, WoS, or other databases does not guarantee this level of completeness; consequently, the following manual procedures required of the author in IRIS become significantly more substantial.

Publications are imported in draft status, so the newly affiliated academic staff member will need to complete the missing data by entering each form and filling in the compulsory fields (marked with an asterisk), as well as the fields that are not compulsory but are strategic from an evaluation point of view (e.g., ASN requires the ISBN to be present to accept a publication; citations, h-index, etc., necessary for VQR and departmental evaluations, are only captured if the WoS and SCOPUS IDs are present in the IRIS tab).

The metadata relating to the PDF attachments already present must also be completed by selecting the appropriate item from the drop-down menu (whether they are editorial, post-print, or pre-print versions; whether dissemination is in open access or is reserved; whether there is a Creative Commons license or an 'All rights reserved' designation, etc.).

If no PDF is already present, it must be attached to all publications dated 2015 or later (see criteria and modalities in Chapter 9).

Once all operations have been completed (see manuals and guidelines in Chapter 17), the records must then be saved and closed in 'Final/In Validation' status. They are automatically synchronized with LoginMIUR (Academic staff site).

If duplicates are generated in LoginMIUR when closing publications, any that do NOT come from IRIS UniTrento must be deleted from LoginMIUR. **At the bottom of each citation, there is a note indicating which database the bibliographic data comes from.**

As a result of the I.R.ID.E. (Italian Researcher ID for Evaluation) Project initiated by ANVUR in 2015 to foster the adoption of ORCID at the national level, IRIS has become one of the applications connected to the National Hub ORCID, from which an author can create or associate their ORCID.

Consequently, if such a creation or association has not yet taken place via one of the applications associated with the National Hub (e.g. an IRIS repository of another university), the first time the author accesses IRIS,

the system will display a screen from which they can [create a new ORCID](#) (which will be automatically communicated to all applications linked to the author's profile), or [associate a pre-existing ORCID with IRIS](#).

7. How to Enter Research Outputs into IRIS

An author must enter their scientific works into IRIS **promptly, and no later than 3 months after the date on which the works are made available** in print or digital form **by the publishers**.

The author has several procedures for entering publications into the Institutional Archive, all starting from the Products Desktop by clicking the New Publication ('Nuova pubblicazione') button. One of the following entry modes can be selected:

- a. Manual submission
- b. Free search (from databases)
- c. Search for identifier (import using identifiers from PubMed, SCOPUS, Crossref, mEDRA, arXiv, WoS, DataCite, DOI, CiNii, ISBN)
- d. Search for author ID (ORCID ID; SCOPUS Author ID)
- e. Upload a file (in **BibTeX, EndNote, CSV, ISI, TSV, RIS** format).

The first option requires the author to enter all metadata (bibliographic citations) and the product's associated data (the work's full-text file; see Chapter 9) manually. The other options allow querying external databases and capturing metadata found in individual databases. The last options will enable products to be imported via files in a format of the author's choice, containing a bibliography extracted from databases.

Once data and metadata input are complete, the records must be saved and closed in the 'Final/In validation' status after acceptance of the [final license](#) (i.e., granting the University of Trento the use of the scientific output for institutional purposes only).

When accessing the Products Desktop, an automatic alert service is activated for new publications by the author in SCOPUS, Web of Science, or ORCID, enabling automatic import. The alert is triggered only if the author has entered their personal ID in the databases listed above within their IRIS profile.

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Each alert displays a list of new publications that have not yet been entered into IRIS by the author, a co-author, or one of their co-authors who has 'recognized' them (see Chapter 8). **The author must initially follow the suggestion of a single database** (e.g., SCOPUS) and avoid imports from other databases (e.g., Web of Science) **until they have finished manually completing each imported record and saved it in its definitive state** (recognizing also each co-author of the University and inserting the PDF file(s) required by the University Policy). This is to **avoid importing duplicates** that the author or co-author will then have to delete manually.

Records entered in IRIS can have different **statuses**:

- **Draft**: when the entry has not yet been completed by the author (this entry is not considered for any evaluation or competition purposes).
- **In validation**: when the author has completed the entry, which still needs to be verified and approved by the librarian/operator (see Chapter 15).
- **Validated**: when the entry has been verified (validated) by the librarian/operator (see Chapter 15).
- **Reopened**: when the author intervenes on the record using the 'Reopen' button, or when the record is reopened by the librarian/operator at the author's request to make any change.
- **Final**: all publications migrated in 'definitive/final' or 'in validation' status from the previous UGOV Institutional Archive, plus some types of products generally not included in VQR evaluation procedures.

All inserted records can be **edited or deleted** using the 'Edit' button ('Back to workspace' to edit, 'Remove' to delete the record). The 'Remove' button is only available for draft records. If the record is already in *Final / Reopened / In validation / Validated* status, deletion must be requested by writing to iris@unitn.it.

All data entered into and retrieved from IRIS are processed in accordance with [GDPR 2016/679](#).

More detailed instructions on how to enter products are available on the [IRIS portal in the Guides for Authors](#) section, particularly [IRIS Manual](#) and [User Guide](#).

8. How to Enter Authors' Names in IRIS

Correctly entering authors' names in the IRIS bibliographic record is a crucial action. In fact, it is not sufficient to enter the authors' names manually (or to import them automatically), but **the authors belonging to the University must be correctly 'linked' to the University's information systems**. Only in this way will each publication be traced back to its author during the **evaluation phase and across all the sites, databases, or external archives to which IRIS provides data** (see Chapter 5).

Properly and accurately indicating author full names in the 'author string' ('Stringa autori') helps link them to the names database (**'recognition' as an author affiliated with the University**), reducing the likelihood of error, especially in the case of homonyms, even partial ones (e.g., if only the first initial of the first name is mentioned).

When entering data manually and before clicking on 'Elabora stringa autori' ('Edit author string'), it is important to always follow the instructions in the note at the bottom of the 'Author(s)' field. It advises, where possible, to use full first names and surnames (initials may be ambiguous during recognition) and to use the provided punctuation (allowing IRIS to identify first names and surnames with certainty, without ambiguity).

Once you click on 'Elabora stringa autori' ('Edit author string'), IRIS will automatically trigger the 'recognition' process. The more precisely names are entered, the less likely they are to have errors when **highlighting in green the authors affiliated with the University**.

When **importing from a database or from files**, the author does not have to type anything, and the 'recognition' operation will start automatically. However, in view of the frequency with which imported names show only the first initial of the first name, or are erroneously written in databases, it is **particularly important for the author always to check the list of recognized internal authors** (in green) and, if necessary, also to **manually recognize those excluded (any authors to be disambiguated, in yellow) or to disconfirm those wrongly identified** as internal authors (usually due to homonymy), turning them grey.

IRIS allows adding pseudonyms to a personal profile (Profile > Personal Data > Alternative names), 'Profilo anagrafico'. If an author has been entered into the University database (thus in IRIS) with a different name compared to the one(s) they use for authorship (e.g., full government name, order of first name/surname,

etc.), it is possible to add all variants to the profile. This enables automatic linking of the name as it appears in the publications with the name in the University database.

Further information or clarifications, including explanations of all ‘recognition’ stages, are available in the manual ‘Author String Management Mode’ ([‘Modalità di gestione stringa autori’](#)) in the ‘Author Guides’ section on the IRIS Home Page (for more operational details, also consult the dedicated section in the CINECA Online Resources ([Risorse online CINECA](#))).

9. How to Attach a PDF to IRIS and the relevant University Policy

Scientific papers published since 2015 must include the full PDF text in IRIS, both for control purposes and internal or ministerial evaluation.

According to the latest [University Policy on Open Science](#), approved by the Academic Senate on 7 December 2022, a PDF of the full text must always be attached in the editorial version (VoR, Version of Record; see ‘Nota Bene’ in Chapter 9) to each record produced in IRIS with a publication date on or after 1 January 2023, for local or national evaluation purposes. If this version is legally disseminated under Open Access, no additional PDFs are required. If, on the other hand, access to the final editorial version must be legally ‘closed’ (i.e., not Open Access), it is strongly recommended – for the purpose of supporting Open Science as a [strategic objective of the University](#) – also to **include a version that can be legally disseminated in Open Access** (e.g., pre-print or refereed author’s post-print; AAM, Author’s Accepted Manuscript; see ‘Nota Bene’ in Chapter 9) (i.e., compatible with the publishing contract or Copyright Transfer Agreement, and/or with the policies described in [Open policy finder](#), and/or with the indications received from the publisher).

Scientific papers **published on 31 December 2022 or before** are governed by the previous [Policy on Open Access to the Scientific Literature](#) regulation, approved by the Academic Senate on 29 January 2014 and amended on 4 March 2020, according to which it is necessary to attach the full PDF text of the publication either as a final **edited version or as a refereed post-print, even in closed access** (if open access is not allowed by the publisher’s policy).

To understand the Open Access policies of major international publishers and journals, please consult the

[Open Policy Finder](#) database, the copyright pages in the publications themselves or on the publishers' websites, and/or the signed publishing contract.

Attachments must be in PDF format and as complete as possible. Local and national Evaluation Committees (e.g., for the ASN, and especially for authors in non-bibliometric fields) require that the attachments also include the paratext (cover page, colophon, table of contents), which is included in the publication file itself.

For each attachment, the author must select an access setting: 'Solo gestori archivio' (Archive Managers Only) in case of permanently closed access, 'Accesso aperto' (Open Access) in the case of legally permitted open access, or 'Embargo' (Open Access only after a date set by the editorial contract and/or journal policy).

Each full text of a scientific paper is also associated with a **usage license** ('All rights reserved', 'Creative Commons', 'Other license'), which enables web readers, users, and viewers to understand the accessibility rules for the file.

For further clarification on the information provided, please refer to the manual '[Inserimento allegati](#)' ('Upload a file') in the 'Guide per Autori' ('Author's Guides') section on the IRIS Home Page. For more operational details, you can also consult the dedicated section '[Risorse online CINECA](#)' ('CINECA Online Resources').

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PREPRINT, POSTPRINT, EDITORIAL VERSION

The versions that can be attached in IRIS are: **pre-print** (corresponding to the author's pre-refereed submitted manuscript), the **refereed post-print** (corresponding to the version accepted by the publisher and already refereed, but without the final editorial graphic layout), and the **editorial version** (i.e., the final publication version, with the publisher's layout and pagination).

Pre-print (*submitted version, non-refereed manuscript, draft, author's original, etc.*). It chronologically precedes the post-print and conveys the content as it appears before being submitted for refereeing, after which it could qualify as suitable for publication, having been corrected following (peer) review. The author has generally chosen fonts, page layout, etc., and/or has aligned them with the journal's submission requirements. In fact, authors sometimes create preprints using a publisher-provided template, which can make them similar to post-prints (though not necessarily the same editorial version)

and may lack peer review.

Post-print (*author's accepted manuscript, refereed author's manuscript, final draft post-refereeing, pre-proof, etc.*): chronologically follows the pre-print and precedes the editorial version. The graphic layout may be similar to the pre-print but may differ from it and, in some cases, follow a publisher-defined template, which can make it similar to the final editorial version. The content has already incorporated the referee's corrections and improvements. A text taken from the published editorial version in which the author deletes content improvements made in the published version should not be considered as a true post-print, nor should a now paginated file from which the author has deleted bibliographical details specific to the material already published (pagination, volume and year markings, copyright, DOI, ...).

Editorial version (*published version, version of record, publisher's layout, editorial PDF, etc.*): this is the already published (online and/or paper) version of a paper, following publication, final and stable in all its parts at the level of contents, layout (conforming to the standards of publishers, journals or publishing series) and bibliographical data (pages, volume or issue, etc.). It can also be uploaded into IRIS as a document for institutional and administrative use when the publisher marks the PDF with expressions such as 'Review Copy', 'Copy for Author Use', 'Not for Redistribution', etc. The editorial version to be entered into IRIS must be the one actually published and not a draft under correction.

10. Archive Quality: Retrieval of Web of Science and SCOPUS Identifiers

With this IRIS functionality, you can automatically check which records in IRIS still lack a Web of Science and/or SCOPUS identifier, which they may require, and assign them without accessing the individual databases.

It is also possible to check whether an IRIS record is linked to an incorrect or obsolete WoS or SCOPUS code, and to create a new link between the publications in IRIS and those in SCOPUS and/or WoS.

IRIS identifies potential matches by querying relevant databases and leveraging publication metadata.

For more details, see the manual '[Inserimento codici SCOPUS e WoS da IRIS: qualità dell'archivio identificativi](#)' ('How to enter SCOPUS and WoS identifiers: Archive Quality: Identifiers') available in the 'Author's Guides' section on the IRIS [Home Page](#).

11. How to Extract Bibliographies from IRIS and from DU Digital University

Metadata from IRIS publications can be used to extract a bibliography from an author's Digital University (DU) page, which draws data from IRIS, or to extract bibliographic data directly from IRIS using bibliographic data management tools.

The extraction process from DU starts at webapps.unitn.it/du: log into 'MyDU' with your University credentials and then click on 'Print Curriculum > Preview'. From here, you can view and print the curriculum with attached bibliography of publications, editable as needed, in .doc format; alternatively, you can print only the bibliography by selecting only the 'Publications' section. Please note that **products in reopened or draft status in IRIS do not appear in DU**. Furthermore, it takes approximately **24-48 hours** for entries and updates made in IRIS to be visible in DU. On the IRIS Home Page, in the 'Guides for authors' section, the guide '[Extracting bibliographies from DU](#)' is available.

To [extract a bibliography directly from IRIS](#), you need to use a bibliographic data management tool, e.g., [Zotero](#) or [Mendeley](#). Publications can be extracted from '**Products > Desktop Products > Export Metadata**', or from '**Advanced Search**' by entering your name as the author, selecting '**Export**', and finally specifying the desired data presentation format.

To convert and process the file thus obtained into an .rtf file using Zotero, follow the instructions provided in the [appropriate CINECA online guide](#).

If you would like to use Mendeley instead, CINECA has prepared additional [brief guidelines](#).

PLEASE NOTE

EXTRACTION OF METADATA FROM IRIS (ADVANCED SEARCH, REPORTING, AND ANALYSIS)

The individual author(s) (from 'Personal view') and the departmental person in charge specifically (from 'Departmental View') can extract bibliographic metadata in IRIS from [Advanced Search](#) or from [Reporting and Analysis > Research Products > P.0.1. List of Publications](#).

Data extracted in this way are:

- not official
- instantaneous (i.e., extracted at the exact date and time of creation of the extracted file)

- obtained with the extraction criteria set by the extractor
- neither comparable nor integrable with any other data, especially if official, received from other Offices and/or sources (see e.g. SMARTM)
- purely operational, for extemporaneous and NON-evaluative checks (some examples of operational uses: checking duplicates; quickly finding ASN data to be corrected; quickly indicating to the helpdesk which publications do not migrate to LoginMIUR; counting publications with files in OA and/or in editorial version, to understand how much there is to correct for H2020/Europe projects; etc.).

In particular, the data extracted in this way cannot in any way be used for any evaluation procedure (e.g., allocations of University/Department/Centre funds; salary increases; career progressions; etc.).

In compliance with the provisions of GDPR 2016/679, as personal data controllers, you may use the data only in the manner and for the sole purposes set out in the IRIS Policy.

Finally, the University has a centralized data extraction system, managed by the Digital Services for Research Office, that produces official, unambiguously valid periodic reports for evaluation and the allocation of human and economic resources. You can contact this Office, which will check whether the specific extraction requirements apply to your request.

12. European Projects in IRIS

For [publications linked to research projects](#) benefiting from [European Union funding](#), depositing in IRIS also ensures that the author(s) will fulfil the obligations regarding access to and dissemination of the results obtained.

IRIS is considered a 'trusted repository' under the Open Science criteria required by the European Union and the funding calls.

[IRIS is also synchronized with OpenAIRE](#), which automatically harvests metadata of publications related to FP7, Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, ERC, and Marie Curie projects weekly. IRIS, therefore, acts as a single data provider, allowing the research team and individual author(s)

- **to save time** by consolidating publication management in a single collector.

- to **avoid the reduction of funding** as a possible consequence if they fail to fulfill any obligation related to evaluations, including open access dissemination of research results.

For information on how to enter EU project data in the IRIS bibliographic record for each product, see CINECA Guide '[ERC Widget, Project - OpenAire](#)'.

13. ASN: IRIS Simulation Report for Candidates and Commissioners

From 'Reportistica e Analisi' (Reports and Analysis Section) in IRIS > ASN Simulation, an author can obtain simulation reports to check whether the thresholds of their GSD (formerly SC)/SSD (or another manually entered GSD (formerly SC)/SSD) have been reached based on the indicators related to their scientific production in IRIS.

The ASN simulation was conducted in accordance with the rules set out in [DM 589/2018](#) and Annex [Table A](#). CINECA, the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, and the IRIS Focus Group contributed to the implementation of the report. They emphasize that the simulation is purely indicative and recommend that the direct author or the third party concerned make consequential use of it, considering all aspects highlighted below.

The report is based on IRIS data and bibliometric indicators as of the date indicated in the report, but does not consider any periods of compulsory leave, which in the ASN application entitle the applicant to percentage increases in values.

In addition, the simulation may differ from the outcome of an ASN application due to errors in cataloguing publications, missing data in IRIS, and/or temporal variability in bibliometric data. Please also note that ANVUR calculates the indicator values based on the latest application date.

CINECA also specifies that the simulation uses public-domain data and algorithms and should therefore be considered only a calculation aid, which can be performed manually or with equivalent tools.

On the [IRIS Home Page](#), in the 'Author's guides section', two short guides are available for the generation of the report by individual authors and Department Directors, for [bibliometric](#) and [non-bibliometric](#) sectors.

The ASN Simulation Report and the criteria adopted for ASN in selecting research products are **also partly used by the University for the [accreditation of research doctorates](#)**.

14. VQR via IRIS

The [Research Quality Evaluation \(VQR\)](#) is the procedure for evaluating the results of scientific research conducted by ANVUR, carried out periodically as part of its institutional activities.

The selection of products to be submitted for VQR takes place via an integrated module in IRIS, which appears in the VQR section.

This module, also called '**IRIS ER VQR**' (where ER stands for '**Evaluation and Review**'), was designed by CINECA to allow the three phases of the VQR to be carried out: selection of publications by the lecturer; resolution of any 'conflicts' by the Department if several co-authors choose the same publication; and creation of a data and metadata package ready for submission to the VQR ministerial site by administrators.

The ER module draws data already entered in IRIS and synchronizes with the IR module to incorporate any necessary changes to each product record gradually. The ER Module also allows authors and Department Directors to fill in a **supplementary record** for each product, which enables them to add to the corresponding record in the IR Catalogue the **metadata required ad hoc by ANVUR and by the individual GEVs** (Groups of Evaluation Experts) for VQR only, as indicated by the Call for Papers and/or by the individual GEV Guidelines. The ER Module also enables visualization of bibliometrics derived from Web of Science and SCOPUS, as well as the production of monitoring reports.

The fourth evaluation exercise ([VQR 2020-2024](#): covering the publication years 2020-2024) was initiated by [Ministerial Decree 998 of 1 August 2023](#), and requires universities to submit research products, research projects, and case studies between January and February 2025. By June 2026, the lists of evaluated products, case studies, and infrastructure reports are expected to be published on the ANVUR website.

Regulations and instructions for the various VQR campaigns are updated each time on the [dedicated ministerial website](#) and consequently applied by CINECA in the specially configured ER Module, as well as communicated to all entitled parties (authors, Directors or Heads of Departments, administrative support staff).

The criteria adopted in the VQR and in the documents of the various GEVs for selecting research products are also partly used by the university to establish the internal criteria for salary increases.

15. Validation in IRIS

The Research Outputs Office staff receive specific training in librarianship, copyright, and Open Science to carry out checks (validation) that safeguard the quality of the data made available for information, statistical, and/or evaluation purposes.

'Validation' is a formal copyright check that has a blocking effect only when the research output has received public funding (e.g., H2020, PRIN). In such cases, the funding body generally requires the attached PDF to be made available in Open Access by a specific deadline. To protect copyright holders, all attachments to IRIS records remain closed-access until the Research Outputs Office staff have reviewed all relevant policies. In these instances, we recommend that authors complete their submissions well in advance and notify the Research Outputs Office staff of their deadlines as soon as they upload the records to IRIS so that they can be prioritized. As a rule of thumb, validation can take up to an hour per record, so it is best to notify the staff in advance.

For all other evaluation purposes, (temporary) non-validation does not constitute an issue: the publication's bibliographic data are regularly displayed and included in the lists that can be evaluated by Departments and Doctoral Schools, Administrative Offices, MUR and ANVUR, provided the record status is 'In validation' (and not 'draft' or 'reopened') and includes the attachment requested by the University Policy (see Chapter 9).

16. Doctoral Theses in IRIS

Doctoral theses must be preserved in IRIS, as a compulsory and binding storage to fulfill the final recognition of the thesis title, stated in the [Linee guida per il deposito delle tesi di dottorato negli archivi aperti](#) ('Guidelines for the Preservation of Doctoral Theses in Open Archives') approved by the CRUI in October 2007, as well as in the [Regolamento di Ateneo in materia di Dottorato di Ricerca](#) ('University Regulation on Doctoral Theses') issued with DR no. 250 of 11 March 2022.

To simplify the process of depositing their theses along with their related [Disclaimer](#), [Guidelines for uploading Doctoral Theses in IRIS](#) are available to doctoral students on the IRIS Home Page under 'Phd Theses' navigation bar.

Entering a thesis in IRIS also includes the mandatory step of uploading a Disclaimer in which the candidate expresses their consent to make their work immediately viewable and available for public consultation. If

Open Access is not immediately possible, the student provides detailed reasons; in this case, the Disclaimer must also be signed by the thesis Supervisor.

In fact, CRUI, as well as the Rectors of Italian Universities, has aligned with international practices that enable the Open Access dissemination of the first publicly funded scientific results achieved by PhD students. In parallel with the publications, it is natural that any transfer of copyright and industrial property rights related to the theses is respected.

To this end, an **embargo of no more than 24 months** is envisaged for doctoral theses to be published by a publisher that does not permit open access before the volume's publication. An embargo is also envisaged if the thesis contains sensitive data, or constitutes a potential danger to public safety, or has been produced as part of projects financed by public or private entities with constraints on the disclosure of the results, or is the subject of any patent application and registration, and/or subject to protection in accordance with the regulations on industrial property.

Doctoral thesis must be **deposited in IRIS by the doctoral student at least 10 days before the scheduled date of the defense**, and is subsequently validated by IRIS staff approximately 10 days after that date. **After this validation**, as a document with both scientific/academic and administrative value, **the doctoral thesis is no longer modifiable/replaceable in any way. The full text only becomes visible after validation.**

IRIS also makes it possible to automatically fulfill the obligation of [Deposito legale delle tesi di dottorato](#) ('Legal Deposit of Doctoral Theses') at the [National Central Libraries of Rome](#) and [Florence](#) (Biblioteche Nazionali Centrali di Roma e Firenze).

17. Handbooks and Tutorial

Supporting materials in Italian (the English version is in preparation) are available to explain how to complete IRIS records.

A. UNIVERSITY DOCUMENTATION SUPPORTING OPEN SCIENCE

Piano Strategico – 2022-27 [Parte I](#) e [parte II Policy di Ateneo sulla Scienza aperta](#) (2022-)

[Policy sull'accesso aperto \(Open Access\) alla letteratura scientifica \(2014-21\)](#)

B. IRIS: GENERAL ASPECTS

[Elenco delle installazioni IRIS](#)

[Libguide IRIS](#)

[Glossario IRIS](#) (CINECA)

[Libguide Open Access: Risorse Open Access di UniTrento](#)

C. IRIS: LICENCE and GDPR

[Licenza IRIS: condizioni da leggere e approvare prima di utilizzare IRIS](#)

[Informativa sul trattamento dei dati personali degli autori delle produzioni scientifiche pubblicate nell'anagrafe di ricerca ad accesso aperto 'IRIS' dell'Università di Trento](#)

D. IRIS: PUBLIC INTERFACE

[IRIS: Portale pubblico](#) (CINECA)

E. IRIS: AUTHOR INTERFACE

[Pagina del Ricercatore \(Il mio profilo pubblico\)](#) (CINECA)

[Ricerca avanzata catalogo prodotti](#)

[Stati della pubblicazione](#)

[MANUALE IRIS: Gestione pubblicazioni – visione personale](#)

[IRIS: Desktop Prodotti Autore](#) (Nuova interfaccia 2022)

[IRIS: Prontuario d'uso](#)

[IRIS: Inserimento nuova pubblicazione](#) (CINECA)

[Controllo duplicati in submission: azioni a disposizione dell'utente in visione personale](#) (CINECA)

F. AUTHOR RECOGNITION (*IRIS* → Sezione 2 - Descrivere)

[Modalità di gestione stringa autori](#)

[Riconoscimento autori](#) (CINECA)

G. HOW TO ATTACH A PDF (*IRIS* → Sezione 4 - Descrivere)

[IRIS: Inserimento allegati](#)

[Upload allegati in submission](#) (CINECA)

H. HOW TO FIND WoS AND SCOPUS CODES FOR MANUAL INPUT

[Come si trovano i codici WoS e SCOPUS](#)

[Inserimento codici SCOPUS e WoS da IRIS: qualità dell'archivio identificativi](#)

[Libguide sulla Bibliometria](#)

I. IRIS and ORCID

[Come creare un nuovo ORCID o associare un ID esistente in IRIS](#)

[Come fare per ottenere un ORCID](#) (CINECA)

[Ho già un ORCID. Come posso associarlo?](#) (CINECA)

[FAQ ORCID](#) (CINECA)

[Push & Pull ORCID](#) (outbound export from IRIS to ORCID and inbound import from ORCID to IRIS)
(CINECA)

J. EXTRACTION OF METADATA OR BIBLIOGRAPHY FILES FROM IRIS

[Estrazione di una bibliografia da IRIS](#) (CINECA)

[Come creare una bibliografia da IRIS: generazione file citazionale con Zotero](#) (CINECA)

[Come creare una bibliografia da IRIS: generazione file citazionale con Mendeley](#) (CINECA)

[Estrazione bibliografie da DU](#)

[Reportistica: concetti base](#) (CINECA)

[Reportistica e Analisi](#) (CINECA)

K. EUROPEAN PROJECTS IN IRIS (*IRIS* → *Sezione 3 - Descrivere*)

[Widget ERC, Project - OpenAire \(Come collegare i progetti europei alla scheda prodotto in IRIS\)](#)
(CINECA)

[IRIS & OpenAIRE](#) (CINECA)

L. ASN IN IRIS

[SIMULAZIONE per l'Abilitazione Scientifica Nazionale ASN](#) (CINECA)

[IRIS Unitn - Tool per la simulazione ASN nei settori bibliometrici](#)

[IRIS Unitn - Tool per la simulazione ASN nei settori non bibliometrici](#)

M. DOCTORAL THESIS IN IRIS

[Linee guida per il deposito delle tesi di dottorato negli archivi aperti](#) (October 2007) / Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane

[Regolamento di Ateneo in materia di Dottorato di Ricerca](#) (March 2022) / Università degli Studi di Trento

[Linee guida per l'inserimento delle Tesi di dottorato in IRIS: modalità di deposito](#)

[Declaratoria IRIS per le tesi di dottorato](#)

18. Contacts

If the information and support provided in the previous chapter are not sufficient to solve critical issues encountered by the author, the Research Outputs Office remains at their disposal for any doubts, problems, or requests for support via email: iris@unitn.it

Departmental contact persons:

https://www.biblioteca.unitn.it/alfresco/download/workspace/SpacesStore/204f5ec5-b37a-4f96-aeb8-705766a0878d/13-09-26_Personale%20di%20riferimento.pdf